

Investigating the role of SymRK interactors in the evolution of root endosymbioses

Vidyashree Shivakumaraswamy¹, Maria Spezzati¹, Martina Ried², Katarzyna Parys¹
and Martin Parniske¹

¹LMU Munich, Faculty of Biology, Biocenter Großhaderner Str. 2 Martinsried, Germany

²IPB Leibniz Institute of Plant Biochemistry, Weinberg 3 Halle, Germany

E-mail: v.shivakumaraswamy@bio.lmu.de

The exchange of nutrients from the soil is most effective and sustainable when plant roots establish a mutually beneficial relationship with soil microbes capable of root endosymbiosis. In exchange for phosphate, plant root cells can host entire structures of fungi, such as arbuscular mycorrhiza (AM), or host rhizobacteria involved in root nodule symbiosis (RNS) for nitrogen. While approximately 80% of land plants can form root endosymbiosis with AM, RNS is restricted to only certain leguminous plants of the order Fabales, Fagales, Cucurbitales and Rosales¹. AM and RNS share some genetic tools for their endosymbiosis, as the plant genes required to accommodate AM are conserved across most land plants, suggesting that RNS genes may have evolved from AM development genes. One of the shared genes, symbiosis receptor-like kinase (SymRK), has been experimentally proven to be necessary for RNS and might have undergone super-functionalization to facilitate nodule structure while still accommodating AM development²⁻⁴. We hypothesise that the critical sequence adaptation of SymRK may lead to differential interactome between RNS and AM root endosymbiosis. To investigate this, we aim to identify the potential interactors of different versions of SymRK using a biased approach of testing known partners⁵⁻¹⁰ initially through quantitative Y2H, followed by FLIM-FRET analysis and Grated Channel interferometry (GCI) to determine their interaction strength. Lotus and tomato SymRK will be used for comparative analysis using an unbiased approach of proteome analysis to identify differential interactors and/or unknown SymRK interactors. The specific role of SymRK interactors in RNS and AM signaling will be determined using Cas-12-based genome-edited higher-order mutant lines of interactors. The ultrastructure of symbiotic phenotypes of mutants will be analyzed using advanced light microscopy. Additionally, interactor mutants will be used for calcium spiking analysis to sort them into inducers or non-inducers of spiking, which is expected to reveal symbiosis signaling independent of calcium spiking. Comparative transcriptome patterns of interactor mutants will also be obtained to explore the evolutionarily converging and diverging molecular players of AM and RNS signaling.

References

1. Parniske M., (2008). *Nat Rev Microbiol* **6**, 763–775.
2. Stracke, Kistner, C., Yoshida, S., Mulder, L., Sato, S., Kaneko, T., Tabata, S., Sandal, N., Stougaard, J., Szczyglowski, K., and Parniske, M. S. *et al.*, (2002). *Nature* **417**, 959–962.
3. Kistner, C. & Parniske, M., (2002). *Trends in Plant Science* **7**, 511–518.
4. Markmann, K., Giczey, G. & Parniske, M. (2008). *PLoS Biol* **6**, e68.
5. Kevei, Z. *et al.*, (2007). *Plant Cell* **19**, 3974–3989.
6. Nagae, M., Parniske, M., Kawaguchi, M. & Takeda, N. (2016). *Plant Physiol* **172**, 2033–2043.
7. Vernié, T. *et al.*, (2016). *Plant Physiol* **170**, 2312–2324.
8. Tóth, K. *et al.*, (2012). *PLoS One* **7**, e30817.
9. Zhu, H. *et al.*, (2008). *Plant Physiol* **148**, 337–347.
10. Chen, T. *et al.*, (2012). *Plant Cell* **24**, 823–838.